

Synthesis, Antifungal Activity and Influence of Structural Changes on the Absorption of Dyes derived from Indolylthiazole

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The synthesis of 2-amino-3-methyl- and 2,3-dimethyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)-thiazoliumiodide (3) has been described. These compounds were condensed with *p*-*N,N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (DAB), other aldehydes and *p*-nitroso-*N,N*-dimethylaniline (NDA) to furnish the corresponding styryl dyes and their aza analogues (4). The influence of substituents and replacement of $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ by $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$, $-\text{N}=\text{C}$ and $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ on the absorption of the dye has been discussed. The antifungal activity of the dyes were evaluated.

THIAZOLE derivatives have significant chemotherapeutic activities¹. The study and the effect of replacement of $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ on the absorption of styryl dyes derived from condensation of 2-methyl quaternary salts with *p*-*N,N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (DAB) and with *p*-nitroso-*N,N*-dimethylaniline (NDA) are well documented². The effect of replacement of $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{N}=\text{CH}-$ has also been studied³. This paper deals with the synthesis of several dyes having thiazole moiety with indolyl substituent with a view to study their antifungal activity and the influence of different structural changes on their absorptions.

3-Chloroacetylindole (1) is prepared by the reaction of indole and chloroacetylchloride in non-aqueous medium which is then condensed with acetamide or thiourea to furnish the corresponding 2-substituted-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoles 2a or 2b. These indolylthiazoles are quaternised with methyl iodide and then condensed with different aromatic aldehydes and NDA to furnish several dyes of the type 4a-d. The dye 4a (R=NMe₂) obtained by the condensation of 2,3-dimethyl-4-indolylthiazolium iodide (3a) and DAB exhibited λ_{max} at 502 nm. The replacement of $\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ (4b; R=NMe₂) caused a bathochromic shift (λ_{max} , 525 nm) whereas replacement by $-\text{N}=\text{CH}-$ (4c; R=NMe₂) caused a hypsochromic shift (λ_{max} , 485 nm). This is quite understandable on the basis of FEMO theory⁴ and Forster rule⁵. A bathochromic shift was observed in the replacement by $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ (4d; R=NMe₂) with a λ_{max} of 545 nm.

2,3-Dimethyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (3a) is condensed with various aromatic aldehydes having different substituents such as chloro, methyl, methoxy, nitro, morpholino, piperidino and pyrrolidino to form the corresponding arylidene derivative (4a). Compared to λ_{max} of dimethylaminostyryl dyes (4a; R=NMe₂), the compounds having the chloro, methyl, methoxy and nitro substituents experience a hypsochromic shift (λ_{max} falls in the range 480–496 nm) whereas the absorptions of compounds having morpholino, piperidino and pyrrolidino substituents suffer a bathochromic shift (λ_{max} values in the range 518–525 nm) simultaneously exhibiting hyperchromic effect. The change in the value of absorption maximum with the change in substituent does not follow a regular order and therefore could not be correlated with Hammett's sigma values; such observations have been reported earlier⁵⁻⁶.

Antifungal activity: The fungicidal activity of some representative compounds were evaluated against *T. mentagraphytes* and *A. niger* as the test fungi on Sabouraud's broth medium. 2-Styryl-3-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodides (4a) were

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

R	M.p. °C	λ_{\max} ($\epsilon_{\max} \times 10^4$)	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	S
Chloro	185	488	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SOH	49.6 (50.2)	3.1 (3.3)	6.0 (6.7)
Methyl	205	486	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ SI	54.5 (55.0)	4.0 (4.2)	6.3 (7.0)
Methoxy	168	496	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ OSI	52.7 (53.2)	3.8 (4.0)	6.2 (6.8)
Nitro	163	481	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ SI	48.8 (49.0)	3.0 (3.3)	6.1 (6.5)
Morpholino	205	518 (2.5)	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ OSI	58.9 (54.4)	4.2 (4.5)	5.4 (6.0)
Piperidino	195	525 (5.3)	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₂ SI	56.2 (56.9)	4.7 (4.9)	5.6 (6.1)
Pyrrolidino	184	520 (4.8)	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ SI	55.6 (56.1)	4.3 (4.7)	5.8 (6.2)

found to have appreciable activity against both the fungi in a concentration of 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Maximum antifungal activity was observed with the compounds (4a) having methoxy, morpholino and piperidino groups at *para*-position in the phenyl ring. Considerable change in the antifungal activity was not observed when chloro, methyl, nitro and pyrrolidino substituents were introduced to *para*-position in the phenyl ring of the styryl dyes (4a).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Uv-visible spectra were recorded on a Beckman 35 spectrophotometer. 3-Chloroacetylindole (1) was prepared by the reported⁷ method.

2-Methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazole (2a): 3-Chloroacetylindole (5.2 g) in hot ethanol was added to acetamide (2 g) in ethanol during 30 min. The reaction mixture was refluxed overnight. The crystalline solid obtained on concentration was filtered off. The base was liberated by dissolving the hydrochloride in water and basifying with a saturated solution of sodium carbonate and it was extracted with methylene chloride. The organic extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 124° (Found: S, 13.8. C₁₂H₁₀N₂S requires: S, 14.9%).

Similarly, 2-amino-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazole (2b) was prepared by taking thiourea in place of thioacetamide, m.p. 255° (Found: S, 14.6. C₁₁H₉N₂S requires: S, 14.9%).

2,3-Dimethyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (3a): A solution of 2-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazole (4.7 g) in dry dimethylformamide (15 ml) and methyl iodide (3.6 g) was heated at 100° for 24 h. On cooling the content to room temperature and on addition of ether (30 ml) a gum separated, which was recrystallised from methanol-ethyl acetate mixture (1:1) to afford the quaternary salt, m.p. 204° (Found: S, 8.8. C₁₅H₁₅N₂SI requires S, 9.0%).

Similarly, 2-amino-3-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (3b) was prepared, m.p. 260° (Found: S, 8.6. C₁₂H₁₂N₂SI requires: S, 9.0%).

2-(p-Dimethylaminostyryl)-3-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (4a; R = NMe₂): A solution of 2,3-dimethyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (3.5 g) and *p*-N,N-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.5 g) in ethanol was boiled for 10 min and a drop of piperidine was added, and further refluxed for 1 h. On concentrating the content and on cooling the solution, the resulting crystals were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 185° (Found: C, 53.8; H, 4.1; S, 5.9. C₂₂H₂₂N₂SI requires: C, 54.2; H, 4.5; S, 6.6%); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 502 nm (ϵ 1.56 \times 10⁴). Other members of the series 4a were prepared in the same manner (Table 1).

2-(p-Dimethylamino- α -azastyryl)-3-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (4b; R = NMe₂): 2,3-Dimethyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (3.5 g) and *p*-nitroso-N,N-dimethylaniline (1.5 g) were condensed by the above method to yield the product, m.p. 222° (Found: C, 50.9; H, 4.1; S, 6.0. C₂₁H₂₁N₂SI requires C, 51.6; H, 4.3; S, 6.6%); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 525 nm (ϵ 9.29 \times 10³).

2-(p-Dimethylamino- β -azastyryl)-3-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (4c; R = NMe₂): 2-Amino-3-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (3.6 g) and *p*-N,N-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.5 g) were condensed by the above method to yield the product, m.p. 260° (Found: C, 51.0; H, 3.9; S, 6.2. C₂₁H₂₁N₂SI requires: C, 51.6; H, 4.3; S, 6.6%); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 485 nm.

2-(p-Dimethylaminophenylazo)-3-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (4d; R = NMe₂): 2-Amino-3-methyl-4-(indol-3'-yl)thiazoliumiodide (3.6 g) and *p*-nitroso-N,N-dimethylaniline (1.5 g) were condensed by the above method to give the highly hygroscopic solid, λ_{\max} (EtOH) 545 nm.

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